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Geomorphological Characterization of the Rangpo River Basin Sikkim Himalaya

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Abstract

The Rangpo River, a significant tributary of the Tista River in East Sikkim, India, showcases diverse geomorphic features shaped by intense tectonic activity, variable lithology, and dynamic fluvial processes. This study analyzes the geomorphological features of the Rangpo River basin using topographic data, visual interpretation from thematic maps, and field validation. The basin is categorized into geomorphic zones—glacial, fluvio-glacial, and fluvial—each associated with distinct landforms such as glacial moraines, highly dissected hills, terraces, and floodplains. The presence of springs, landslides, and structural controls (e.g., ridges, faults, scarps) further influence channel morphology and sediment transport. The results indicate a complex interaction between tectonics and geomorphology, which has important implications for sustainable land use planning and hazard mitigation in the Rangpo River valley.

Keywords Geomorphological Characterization, Rangpo River Basin, Sikkim Himalaya.

Introduction

The Rangpo River, flowing through the southeastern part of the Sikkim Himalaya, is a geomorphologically active tributary of the Tista River. Rangpo river basin is located in east Sikkim, India. It lies between latitudinal extent is 27° 04' 49.59" N to 27° 24' 55.55" N and longitudinal extent is 88° 31' 16.43" E to 88° 52' 52.85" E in the eastern Himalayan region. The total area of the Rangpo river basin is 569.50 km². Given the regions fragile geological structure and heavy monsoonal rainfall, the river basin exhibits significant geomorphic diversity.

Objective of study

This study aims to analyze the geomorphic features of the Rangpo River and assess the influence of structural and climatic controls on its channel morphology.

Review of Literature

The Himalayan landscapes, structure created by tectonic process, seismic pattern, and neo tectonic faults are all determined by the dynamics of this collision. Geologists have done a lot of research on Himalaya, looking at things like collision and convergence, subduction rate, past earthquakes, and faulting due to tectonism (Lave et al., 2005; Malik and Mathew, 2005; Bhattacharyya and Mitra, 2009; Kothyari, 2010; Kothyari et al., 2010; Kumar et al., 2010).

Methodology

This research is based on geomorphological mapping using topographic sheets, satellite imagery, and field observations. A detailed interpretation of the geomorphological map based on source Geological Survey of India (<http://bhukosh.gsi.gov.in/>) scale 1:150000 and Topographical maps - Survey of India (<http://www.soinakshe.uk.gov.in>) scale 1:50,000, was conducted to identify landforms, lithological features, and structural elements. Data were categorized into geomorphic units and analyzed in GIS for slope, drainage, and elevation parameters.

Study Area

The Rangpo River basin is located in East Sikkim and drains southward to meet the Tista River. The basin extends from the snow-covered zones in the north (near Kupup and Gnathang) to the foothills in the south (near Rangpo town). It includes key settlements like Pakyong, Rongli, Rorathang, and Rhenock. The elevation ranges from approximately 450 m to over 4450 m, with distinct topographic and geological zones.

Figure 1 shows the various geomorphic units, elevation ranges, structural features, and hydrography of the Rangpo River basin

Analysis

Geomorphological Units and Features

1. Glacial and Snow-Cover Zones

The northern part of the basin shows evidence of glacial processes, with snow-covered areas and glacial lakes near Kupup and Gnathang. These areas have minimal vegetation and are dominated by periglacial and nivation processes.

2. Highly and Moderately Dissected Hills

The majority of the basin is covered with dissected hills, particularly in the central and eastern sections. These are characterized by steep slopes, high relief, and intense fluvial incision. Structural controls such as faults and folds influence the drainage patterns and slope stability.

3. Terraces and Valleys

Terraces are prominent in the mid-reaches near Rorathang, Pakyong, and Rhenock. These fluvial terraces represent former floodplain levels, indicating vertical incision and tectonic uplift. Broad valleys with alluvial fill dominate the southern parts, contributing to fertile agricultural lands.

4. Structural Elements and springs

The geomorphology of the Rangpo basin is heavily influenced by geological structures—ridges, scarps, and foliated zones. Numerous springs emerge along structural

discontinuities, indicating the role of lineaments in groundwater emergence.

5. Landslides and Hazard Features

Landslides are widespread, especially along steep scarps and road cuts. These are triggered by intense rainfall and are closely linked with the dissected hill slopes and anthropogenic modifications.

Channel Morphology

The Rangpo River exhibits a youthful stage with features such as narrow V-shaped valleys, waterfalls, and frequent channel shifts. The longitudinal profile shows steep gradients in the upper reaches and gentler slopes downstream. Tributary confluences near Rorathang and Rhenock influence sediment load and channel planform.

Result and Discussion

The geomorphology of the Rangpo River reflects an intricate balance between tectonics, climate, and human intervention. The presence of old terraces and active landslides signals ongoing uplift and erosion. Channel morphology is rapidly evolving due to high sediment supply from hill slopes, making the river vulnerable to flash floods and bank erosion.

Conclusion

The Rangpo River basin is a dynamic geomorphic system shaped by glacial remnants, structural controls, and active fluvial processes. A comprehensive understanding of its geomorphology is essential for effective watershed management, disaster preparedness, and infrastructure planning in this fragile Himalayan environment.

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